

LIVING WITH PARENTS

We identify the share of individuals who still live with their parents, based on data from the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) collected from 2017 to 2025.

Across 16 countries and regions, the share of people aged 18-34 still living with their parents ranges from 11.1% in Finland to 41.3% in Croatia, showing large regional differences.

Among those aged 18-24, the rate varies from 23.2% (Finland) to 59.5% (Kazakhstan), while for 25-34-year-olds it ranges from 2.8% (Finland) to 37.5% (Taiwan).

In all countries and regions, younger individuals (18-24) are more likely to still live with their parents, but the extent of change between age groups differs. For instance, Germany, Austria and Uruguay show a sharp drop as people move into their late twenties and early thirties, whereas in Taiwan the difference is more modest and in Hong Kong is not significant.

PERCENTAGE OF PEOPLE STILL LIVING WITH THEIR PARENTS

GGs OFFERS VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO VARIOUS LIVING ARRANGEMENTS.

Source: Generations and Gender Survey Round II – wave 1 (data from 2017-2025)

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